

DEVELOPMENT OF SPIRITUAL KNOWLEDGE SLOWDOWN AND ITS DESTRUCTIVE NATURE

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Abstract: In the XXI century, a number of constructive changes have taken place in the spiritual sphere of society. At the same time, destructive processes are also taking place in this area. The most significant among them are related to slowdown in the development of spiritual knowledge. These spiritually destructive processes remove the process of spiritual production from the needs of society, weaken the process of production of socially significant knowledge and ideas, reduce the level of awareness of society members about new knowledge and ideas, form erroneous public opinion, create negative changes in people's spiritual needs, form negative trends in social psychology and ideology.

Keywords: destruction, spiritual destruction, spiritual production, forms of social consciousness, social psychology, ideology, slowing down the development of spiritual knowledge.

The constructive and destructive processes that took place in various fields changed the attitude of the members of the society to the economic, political and social reality. People began to imagine the essence of socio-economic and political processes in a different way, they began to evaluate them differently. Such changes in the human spiritual world legitimately led to a radical renewal of the spiritual sphere of society. The process of meaning production in modern society, the character of forms of social consciousness, the nature of social psychology, and the ideological situation are changing dramatically. As in all fields, these updates show a number of constructive and destructive aspects, processes, situations.

First of all, it should be noted that in the second half of the 20th century and the first quarter of the new century, many constructive processes took place in the spiritual sphere of modern society. These processes are characterized by their diversity, of course. In particular, during the next half century:

the quality of spiritual production has changed; in particular, today this process is implemented on the basis of completely new norms, principles, and resources. The process of creating knowledge, ideas, theories, doctrines, and values has improved both technically and technologically. As a result, the process of spiritual production literally became a factor that develops various spheres of society's life and fully satisfies people's spiritual needs;

forms of social consciousness are rich; in particular, new and new political, legal, ethical, aesthetic, religious, scientific, philosophical and other ideas, knowledge, ideas, theories, doctrines, values of social importance were created. The extent of the influence of these knowledges and imaginations on social existence is extremely widened;

social psychology is rationalized; in particular, the amount of knowledge, customs, and traditions based on reason and logic in its content is increasing, and the share of mystical and irrational elements is decreasing. True, this process is happening in different societies at different rates and scales. But it should be recognized that the place of the mystical world-view is replaced by a rational world-view as one of the most debilitating trends of today;

ideological pluralism has emerged; in particular, when thinking in a global context, the human society escaped the domination of a single ideology. The areas under the rule of a single ideology are decreasing more and more, moreover, alternative ideas and ideologies can be seen forming in these areas. Such ideological pluralism should be accepted as an achievement of human society without a doubt.

At the moment, instead of constructive processes, destructive processes are taking place in the spiritual sphere of modern society. One of the most important of them is related to the slowing down of the development of spiritual knowledge. V.G. Torosyan and N.E. Drobyazkolar's article reveals the nature, structure and development characteristics of spiritual knowledge especially vividly. Experts recall that the concepts of "otium" and "negotium" were in circulation in antiquity. They say that "nego-tium" includes any type of economic activity, while "otium" consists

of activities that serve the spiritual growth of a person, not work-related activities. These types include, for example, reading, music, philosophy, poetry, mathematics, astronomy. Knowledge of these areas served to describe society and human existence, to determine the causes and consequences of events and processes in society, as well as to ensure the formation of a person as a person and his spiritual growth. This spiritual knowledge, which includes intellectuality, aesthetics and morality, is described as the central factor that forms a free citizen. Until the second half of the last century, they even served as a source for determining the social status of a person.

But from the second half of the 20th century, the situation began to change radically. As we noted, the settlement of the foundations of the market economy increased attention to the creation of knowledge of practical importance, capable of generating income in the short term. As a result, the spiritual knowledge that serves to shape the worldview of a person has remained in the shadows. The volume of allocations to research projects that serve to form practical knowledge has increased, and the financing of research into social and humanitarian sciences that create spiritual knowledge has steadily decreased. It can also be seen from the composition of the countries' investments in the development of science. For example, according to official data, 118 billion dollars were allocated for scientific research in the USA in 2019. In the same year, 322 billion dollars were spent on science in China. According to data provided by Eurostat, the European Dog Federation allocated 306 billion euros for these purposes in 2019.

In Russia, expenses for scientific research amounted to 6 billion dollars. It is noteworthy that only a small percentage of these allocations was spent on financing social and humanitarian sciences, creators of spiritual knowledge. For example, in Russia in 2007, 2.3 percent of the funds allocated for research and development funding went to social sciences, and 1.3 percent to humanities. This indicator has not changed significantly in the following years. A similar situation can be seen in other countries. Disproportionate financial provision, the priority of

the principle of income in the distribution of funds has led to a slowdown in the development of social and humanitarian sciences and the development of spiritual knowledge in a situation where technical sciences are developing rapidly. This is one of the main reasons why in the following years, the doctrines and theories of global significance did not appear in the field of social and humanitarian sciences.

This situation is causing serious social consequences in modern society. In particular, the slowdown in the development of spiritual knowledge reduces the ability to describe, describe, classify socio-economic, political and spiritual-cultural processes in human society, to clarify their causes and consequences, to make predictions about their future development, and to manage social events on a scientific basis. . The lack of spiritual knowledge also hinders the identification and expression of factors that have a negative impact on the spiritual image of a person, as well as finding ways to eliminate them.

In short, one of the reasons for the situations noted by many experts as signs of spiritual degradation of the society and the individual is due to the slowing down of the development of spiritual knowledge. To sum up, many constructive processes took place in the spiritual sphere of human society in the 21st century. At the moment, instead of constructive processes, destructive processes are taking place in this area. The most important of such processes is related to the slowing down of the development of spiritual knowledge.

This spiritual-destructive process disconnects the process of spiritual production from the needs of society, weakens the process of production of socially important knowledge and ideas, lowers the level of awareness of new knowledge and ideas of society members, forms wrong public opinion, people are morally creates negative changes in their needs, creates negative trends in social psychology and ideology.

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